

DEVELOPER OF GYMNASTICS EDUCATION TYPES.

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Annotation: This article provides information about developmental types of gymnastics education. This training includes information on the division into basic gymnastics, practical gymnastics, and rhythmic gymnastics.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена информация о развивающих видах гимнастического обучения. Этот тренинг включает в себя информацию о разделении на базовую гимнастику, практическую гимнастику и художественную гимнастику.

BASIC GYMNASTICS. Basic gymnastics is one of the independent types of gymnastics and is the most appropriate means of physical education of people of different ages. It has a place in the curriculum of preschool, school, academic lyceum, secondary special and higher educational institutions, as it corresponds to the tasks of physical education of students in terms of its content and direction. Among the various tools of basic gymnastics, you can choose exercises that can be performed by young, middle-aged and older children, and elderly people.

The health function of basic gymnastics. Basic gymnastics is a great and healthy way to harmoniously develop all the internal and external organs and networks of a person, to strengthen the health of the participants, to increase and improve the body's resistance to the external environment, to increase vital activity, work ability and productivity, to form the correct figure and to develop the physical qualities of the participants. - is of hygienic importance. The mentioned movement skills are of great importance for people's labor and military activities. Learning

them enriches the experience of movement, allows you to develop strength, speed, agility and endurance.

Basic gymnastics is an effective means of enriching the experience of movement. Elements of many movements are learned during basic gymnastics training. After mastering the composition of exercises, which are different in terms of structure and technique, the participants will be able to successfully acquire new forms of movement and perform various movement tasks. This is explained by the law of higher nervous activity, that is, on the basis of existing conditioned reflexes, new higher-level conditioned reflexes are formed.

PRACTICAL GYMNASTICS. Sports and practical gymnastics. Sports-practical gymnastics is a component of general and special physical training in various sports. It is used to improve physical qualities and increase the functional capacity of the athlete's body.

Sports-practical gymnastics is widely used as a means of improving general and special physical fitness. With the help of gymnastic exercises, it is possible to selectively affect the development of the activity of different branches of the body (different muscle groups, separate parts of the body, organs, etc.) and, taking into account the personal characteristics of the athlete, the volume and effectiveness of the physical load can be maximally varied. This makes it possible to use it as the most important and unique means of increasing the results of sports-practical gymnastics.

RHYTHMIC GYMNASTICS. Rhythmic gymnastics is considered one of the forms of physical training in the direction of health. Its main content is running, jumping, and home performances.

All this helps to improve health. He is understandable to everyone, highly impressive and cheerful. Everyone can do rhythmic gymnastics - men and women of different ages and abilities.

Movement in rhythmic gymnastics is unlimited, it affects all parts of the body, agility, dexterity, flexibility, endurance.

Musical rhythm organizes movements and raises the mood of the participants.

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